

Proactive Approach to Innovation Management

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Abstract : The focus of this paper is to compare common approaches for Systems of Innovation (SI) and identify proactive alternatives for driving the innovation. Proactive approaches will also consider short and medium term perspectives with developments in the field of Computer Technology and Artificial Intelligence. Concerning computer technology and large connected information systems, it is reasonable to predict that during current or the next century, intelligence and innovation will be separated from the constraints of human-driven management. After this happens, humans will no longer be driving the innovation and there is possibility that SI for new intelligent systems will set its own targets and exclude humans. Over long time scale, these developments could result in a scenario, which will lead to the development of larger, cross galactic (universal) proactive SI and Intelligence.

Keywords : artificial intelligence, DARPA, Moore's law, proactive innovation, singularity, systems of innovation

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